

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul¹, Sukaria Sinulingga², Fadli³, Sugih Arto⁴, Syafrizal Helmi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Master Of Management Graduate School, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan

Corresponding Email: ekafarahdewis@gmail.com

Received : 10 March 2026

Accepted : 01 April 2026

Revised : 15 March 2026

Published : 18 April 2026

Abstract

This study aims Optimal and excellent public service, the expectation of all citizens, serves as a benchmark for the performance of public service institutions/agencies. Describing public dissatisfaction with public services will consistently inform government improvements in evaluating implemented policies To achieve these goals, good, high-quality service is required. Because good, quality service can help the government achieve these goals. Service is crucial for every citizen, as the better the quality of service provided, the greater the public's trust in the government operating in that service sector. Service standards are benchmarks used as guidelines for service delivery and as a reference for assessing service quality as an obligation and promise of service providers to the public in the context of providing quality, fast, easy, affordable, and orderly services. , a hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, where the problem statement can be a statement about the relationship between two or more variables, comparisons, or independent variables

Keywords: *Calibration, Expectation, Improvements, Implemented policies.*

INTRODUCTION

Optimal and excellent public service, the expectation of all citizens, serves as a benchmark for the performance of public service institutions/agencies. Describing public dissatisfaction with public services will consistently inform government improvements in evaluating implemented policies. According to Sinambela (2014), service is an activity or sequence of activities that occurs in direct interaction between one person and another or a physical machine, and provides customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, the Big Indonesian Dictionary defines service as the act, method, or result of serving. Every government agency is established to achieve a goal: to satisfy the public. Only when these goals are achieved can it be considered a success. To achieve these goals, good, high-quality service is required. Because good, quality service can help the government achieve these goals. Service is crucial for every citizen, as the better the quality of service provided, the greater the public's trust in the government operating in that service sector. Service standards are benchmarks used as guidelines for service delivery and as a reference for assessing service quality as an obligation and promise of service providers to the public in the context of providing quality, fast, easy, affordable, and orderly services. The existence of Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services certainly provides direction to all service providers, both state administrators, BUMN (State-Owned Enterprises), BUMD (Regional-Owned Enterprises), BHMN (State-Owned Legal Entities) to the private sector and individuals to provide standardized services by fulfilling the service standard components (<https://ombudsman.go.id>).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review According to Sinambela (2013), public service is any activity carried out by the government towards a number of people who have any activity that is beneficial in a group or unit, and offers satisfaction even though the results are not tied to a physical product. The definition of public service according to the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Decree Number 25 of 2004 is all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to fulfill the needs of service recipients, or in the context of implementing the provisions

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

of laws and regulations. Meanwhile, the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Decree Number 58 of 2002 groups three services from agencies and BUMN/BUMD. The grouping of these types of services is based on the characteristics and nature of the activities and the service products produced, namely (1) administrative services, (2) goods services, (3) service services. **Previous Research** Many previous researchers have conducted research on service standards, public services, and service quality. This study references previous studies related to the current study. **Conceptual Framework** The conceptual framework will theoretically connect the independent variables with the dependent variables. Calibration laboratory strives to increase customer satisfaction by implementing service quality. The service quality implemented includes reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. In the quality of service, reliability in providing the main service with a fast and impartial service process. Responsiveness is an important service in the service process, the servant is required to be alert and ready to immediately serve consumers when needed. Assurance is a form of providing quality service in accordance with the commitment by giving trust to consumers, ensuring the safety and comfort of consumers in getting service. Empathy is needed in fulfilling consumer satisfaction related to the forms of attitude and concern in providing service to consumers. In addition, physical evidence (tangibles) is important for consumers, this is what gives consumers an appreciation in seeing the availability of facilities, facilities and equipment.

Research Hypothesis In research, a hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, where the problem statement can be a statement about the relationship between two or more variables, comparisons, or independent variables (Sugiyono, 2017). By testing the hypothesis and confirming the predicted and expected relationships, solutions can be found to address the problem at hand. Based on the problem statement and conceptual framework presented above, the following temporary hypothesis can be formulated:

1. Reliability has a significant impact on service quality.
2. Responsiveness has a significant influence on service quality.
3. Assurance has a significant impact on service quality.
4. Empathy has a significant influence on service quality.
5. Physical evidence (tangibles) has a significant influence on service quality.

METHOD

Types of research The type of research conducted in this study is associative research. Associative research is research that connects two or more variables. In this research, there are variables, namely: reliability X1, responsiveness X2, assurance X3, empathy X4, tangibles X5 on the quality of service (Y) of the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit (BPSMB). **Research Location** This research was conducted at the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit (BPSMB). The research period was three months. **Research Population and Sample** According to Priyono (2008) "population is the entire phenomenon/unit that is to be studied." In this study, the population used was consumers who had used Calibration services since 2019. On study This Which become population study are all customers who have used calibration services at the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification UPT Laboratory in 2020, totaling 268 people (Source: Calibration Administration, 2021). The sampling technique used a non-probability sampling method, namely a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or chances for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample (Situmorang, 2017). The type of non-probability sampling method used is purposive sampling, namely a sampling technique that is determined intentionally by the researcher based on certain criteria or considerations. The sample criteria determined in this study are consumers who use Calibration services. For example, a study with 95% confidence, then the error rate is 5%. So the researcher can meet the requirement of a 5% margin of error (0.05) by entering the margin of error into the Slovin formula. To determine the required sample size, the Slovin formula is used, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Information :

n = Desired sample size

N = Population Size

e = Tolerable margin of error

So the number of samples becomes:

$$n = \frac{268}{1 + 268 (0,05)^2} = 160 \text{ orang}$$

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

Data collection technique The data collection methods used in this study are as follows:

1. A questionnaire is a method of collecting data by asking written questions in the form of a questionnaire to respondents about the variables used in the research.
2. Documentation Study is a data collection method by collecting and studying data obtained from books, journals and articles related to the research being conducted.

Operational Research Variables According to Sugiyono (2015), operational research variables are attributes, characteristics, or values of an object or activity with specific variations that researchers have determined to study and draw conclusions from. Definitions of research variables must be formulated to avoid errors in data collection.

Research Instruments In this study, the measurement used a Likert scale according to Sugiyono (2012), a Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of an individual or group of people about social phenomena. The Likert scale variables will be measured and described into variable indicators, then these indicators will be used as the basis for compiling instrument items that can be in the form of questions or statements.

Validity and Reliability Test According to Sinulingga (2014), data validity is a measure that refers to the degree of correspondence between collected data and actual data in the data source. Valid data will be obtained if the data collection instrument is also valid. Validity tests are used to determine the appropriateness of items in a questionnaire or statement in defining variables. The next step is statistically, the correlation number obtained by looking at the asterisk on the total score results, or comparing it with the correlation-free number r value indicates validity. In this study, the validity test will be conducted using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) program.

Table Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,867	16

Source: Research Results, 2021 (Processed Data)

Based on Table, it can be seen that the Alpha coefficient result is greater than 0.60. Thus, all 16 (sixteen) questions are declared reliable and can be distributed to respondents to be used as research instruments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result The results of this study will present a description of the characteristics of the research respondents, a description of the respondents' answers to each research variable.

Gender and Age Crosstab The results of the crosstab for gender and age can be seen in Table below.

Table Gender and Age Crosstab

Gender * Age Crosstabulation						
Count						
		Age				Total
		20-30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years	
Gender	Man	23	47	31	11	112
	Woman	28	16	4	0	48
Total		51	63	35	11	160

Source: Research Results, 2021 (processed data)

Table shows that there are 51 respondents aged 20-30 years, with 23 male and 28 female. There are 63 respondents aged 31-40 years, with 47 male and 16 female. There are 35 respondents aged 41-50 years, with 31 male and 4 female. There are 11 respondents aged 51-60 years, with an average of 11 male respondents.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis This method is an extension of simple regression. Multiple Linear Regression

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

is intended to determine the linear relationship between several independent variables (*reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, tangibles*) with the dependent variable (service quality). The data was processed statistically for analysis and hypothesis testing purposes using the SPSS program tool.

Table Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	,642a	,412	,393	1,217
a. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibles, Assurance, Empathy, Responsiveness, Reability				

Source: Research Results, 2021 (processed data)

The table above shows that R = 0.642, indicating a 64.2% relationship between Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, Assurance, and Tangibles and Service Quality. This indicates a strong relationship.

Classical Assumption Test The normality test is used to test or measure whether, in a regression model, the independent variable and the dependent variable, or both, have a normal distribution. A regression model is appropriate if the distribution is normal or nearly normal. This study tested the level of normality of the data using PP Plots and Histograms.

Source: Research Results, 2021 (processed data)

Based on the PP Plot image above, it can be concluded that the PP Plot graph shows a distribution pattern that is close to normal, where the data distribution is close to the diagonal line. Furthermore, to support the PP Plot results, the researchers tested it using a histogram.

Source: Research Results, 2021 (processed data)

Based on the graph, it can be concluded that the data distribution is normal because the histogram graph shows a normal distribution pattern, so the regression model meets the assumption of normality and vice versa if the data spreads far from the diagonal line and does not follow the direction of the diagonal line or the histogram graph does not show a normal data distribution pattern that does not deviate to the right or to the left.

This test aims to examine and determine whether the independent variables are correlated with each other. To detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity symptoms between independent variables in the regression model, Variance Inflation Factors (VIV) and Tolerance are used with the Tolerance criteria. If the VIF value is 0.10 or <10,

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

then there is no multicollinearity (correlation).

Table Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficientsa			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Reliability	,319	3,138
	Responsiveness	,418	2,391
	Assurance	,555	1,801
	Empathy	,566	1,766
	Tangibles	,448	2,234
a. Dependent Variable: Service Quality			

Source: Research Results, 2021 (processed data)

Table above shows that the Tolerance value of the variable *Reliability* of 0.319, Responsiveness of 0.418, Assurance of 0.555, Empathy of 0.566, and Tangibles of 0.448 are greater than 0.10. The VIF value of the R variable *reliability* of 3.138, Responsiveness of 2.391, Assurance of 1.801, Empathy of 1.766, and Tangibles of 2.234 are smaller than 10, so it can be concluded that there is no correlation or relationship between the independent variables between the independent variables.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion carried out in this research, the researcher draws the following conclusions:

1. The Reliability variable does not have a significant effect on the Quality of Service at the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit, this indicates that customers are less satisfied with the services provided, the predetermined schedule is not appropriate. To increase the reliability variable, the calibration laboratory must ensure that employees have a high commitment in serving customers, by treating employees well, employees will be more loyal and work as well as possible.
2. The Responsiveness variable significantly influences Service Quality at the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit. It is known that customers are satisfied with the accuracy of employees/staff in quickly and responsively serving customer complaints, speed in transactions, and responding to customer complaints.
3. The Assurance variable does not significantly influence the Quality of Service at the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit. It can be seen that employees do not yet have extensive knowledge of the services provided, the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit must provide training and motivation to employees so that they have good knowledge when working. In fostering a sense of comfort and trust in the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit, employees are often expected to be polite and smile. In addition, the good reputation of the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit will provide a sense of security for customers in conducting transactions and the emergence of trust in consumers.
4. The Empathy variable has a significant effect on the Quality of Service at the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit, this shows that customers can feel the sincerity given by the employees in the service provided.
5. The Tangibles variable has a significant effect on the Quality of Service at the Calibration Laboratory of the Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit. It can be seen that customers are satisfied with the provision of neatness of the room layout, availability of equipment, and neatness of employees.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of testing and analysis in this study, the following research suggestions can be formulated:

Publish by **Radja Publika**

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

1. This study found that the reliability variable had no significant effect on service quality. Calibration laboratories are expected to deliver services within the promised timeframe to ensure customer satisfaction.
2. This study found that responsiveness significantly influences service quality in calibration laboratories. It is hoped that calibration laboratories can provide training to increase employee knowledge. This training is expected to improve service quality and enable employees to be more responsive to customer requests.
3. In this study, it has been found that the assurance variable does not have a significant effect on Service Quality, so the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit must provide training and motivation to employees so that they have good knowledge when working. In fostering a sense of comfort and trust in the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit, employees are often expected to be polite and smile. In addition, the good reputation of the Calibration Laboratory of Medan Goods Quality Testing and Certification Unit will provide a sense of security for customers in conducting transactions and the emergence of trust in consumers.
4. This study found that empathy significantly influences service quality. It is hoped that calibration laboratories will provide more individual attention by providing customer care and customer service to ensure customer satisfaction and provide every convenience.
5. In this study, it was found that tangible variables have a significant effect on service quality. The laboratory must improve physical facilities in the form of customer parking facilities and comfortable waiting room facilities so that customers feel satisfied with the services provided.

REFERENCES

- A. Parasuraman, Valarie A. Z, & Leonard LB (1988). "SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality". *Journal of Retailing*. Vol 64 (1) pp 12- 37.
- Armstrong, K. (2015). "Marketing an Introducing Prentice Hall twelfth edition", England : Pearson Education, Inc.
- Ariyanti, N. (2015). "The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction Using Linear Regression Method Case Study of PT. Bank Central Asia Tbk Kalimalang Branch".
- Astuti, H. (2007). "Consumer Satisfaction Analysis (SERVQUAL Model and Important Performance Analysis Model)"
- Atmoko, T. (2011). *Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and Performance Accountability of Government Agencies at Unpad, Bandung*.
- Atmoko, T. (2010). *Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and Performance Accountability of Government Agencies*.
- Azhari, K. (2018). "The Influence of Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction of Go-Jek Service Users in Medan City".
- Badjamal, FA (2019). "The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Values Staying at Simple Lodging in Tinombo District".
- Brilliance HI, & Sherly, T. (2019). "The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at PT Hastaco Tour and Travel".
- Blog. (2013). UPTD. BPSMB Medan <http://bpsmbmedan.blogspot.com/>.
- Dabholkaret.all. (1996). *A measure of Service Quality for Retail Stores: Development and Validation*, *Journal of The Marketing Science*.
- Friedrich, Carl J, *Man and His Government*, McGraw-Hill, New York. (2002).
- Januar E. P, Ai LY (2016). "The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at JNE Bandung Branch".
- Jones, CO (2015). *Introduction to Public Policy*, Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning "Public Services. Jakarta: Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia; 2009".
- Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia. *General Guidelines for Compiling Public Satisfaction Indexes for Government Service Units*. Jakarta: Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform. (2004).
- Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63/2003 concerning Guidelines for Service Provision.
- Kotler, P, Gary A. (2012). *Principles of Marketing*, 12th Edition. Volume 1. Jakarta: Erlangga.

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SERVICE STANDARD POLICIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN THE CALIBRATION LABORATORY OF THE TESTING AND TESTING UPT MEDAN GOODS QUALITY CERTIFICATION

Eka Farra Dewi Sitompul **at al.**

- Kotler, P. & Gary A. (2014). Principles Of Marketing, 15th edition. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, P., Kevin L. K. (2016). Marketing Management, 15th Global Edition, Pearson Prentice Hall. New Jersey.
- Kuzairi, U. (2018). "Implementation of Minimum Service Standards (SPM) in Public Services in the Health Sector (Case Study at Dr. H. Koesnadi Bondowoso General Hospital)".
- Mahmudi. (2010). *Public Sector Performance Management*. Jakarta. STIE YKPN.
- Mukarom, Z., & Muhibudin WL (2015). Public Service Management. Bandung: CV Pustaka Setia.
- Paramitasari, N. (2016). "Analysis of Service Quality Using the Servqual Method in the New Student Admissions Section of the Darmajaya Institute of Informatics and Business, Bandar Lampung".
- Pasolong, H. (2010). Public Administration Theory, Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Purwanto. (2012). Quantitative Research Methodology for Psychology and Education. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar Offset.
- Putri, K., Nurcaya, IN (2013). "The Influence of Service Quality Dimensions on Customer Satisfaction at D&I Skin Centre Denpasar".
- Sinambela, L. (2014). Public Service Reform. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Situmorang, SH, Lufti, M. (2014). Data Analysis for Management and Business Research.
- Tjiptono, F. (2000). Service Management, Third Edition, Andi Offset, Yogyakarta.
- Van Meter, Donald and Van Horn, Carl E. (1975). The Policy Implementation Process Conceptual Frame Work. Journal of Administration and Society
- Wikipedia. (2021). <https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kalibrasi>.